

Transceiver for Differential Wave Pipe-Lined Serial Interconnect with Surfing

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Abstract : In the literature, surfing technique has been proposed for single ended wave-pipelined serial interconnects to increase the data transfer rate. In this paper a novel surfing technique is proposed for differential wave-pipelined serial interconnects, which uses a 'Controllable inverter pair' for surfing. To evaluate the efficiency of this technique, a transceiver with transmitter, receiver, delay locked loop (DLL) along with 40 nm metal 4 interconnects using the proposed surfing technique is implemented in UMC 180nm technology and their performances are studied through post layout simulations. From the study, it is observed that the proposed scheme permits 1.875 times higher data transmission rate compared to the single ended scheme whose maximum data transfer rate is 1.33 GB/s. The proposed scheme has the ability to receive the correct data even with stuck-at-faults in the complementary line.

Keywords : controllable inverter pair, differential interconnect, serial link, surfing, wave pipelining

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